

Studies on effective decomposition of monazite minerals by variety of phosphate fluxes for simple and direct determination of uranium by LED fluorimeter

Leela Gopal, V. V. Hanuman and G. Chakrapani*

Chemistry Laboratory, Atomic Minerals Directorate for Exploration and Research, Begumpet,
Hyderabad-500 016, India

E-mail : chakrapanigotur@yahoo.com Fax : 91-40-27762940

Abstract : A simple, rapid, effective sample decomposition method is developed for the determination of uranium (U) in monazite minerals by fluorimetric (Light Emitting Diodes (LED) based) technique. The salts of sodium di hydrogen phosphate (NaH_2PO_4), di sodium hydrogen phosphate (Na_2HPO_4) and tetra sodium pyrophosphate ($\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$) were used to conduct studies on effective decomposition and dissolution of monazite minerals. The flux shortlisted for sample decomposition has several advantages. The fusion is very simple (involve minimal skills), time saving and eco-friendly (no acids were used for sample dissolution), where as in the reported conventional sample decomposition methods involving fusion with sodium peroxide, mixture of KHF_2 and NaF, mineral acids are being used for sample decomposition to get clear solution. Further this solution cannot be used directly for uranium determination by LED fluorimetry; hence separation is required, resulting in low sample throughput. In the present method no such separation is required as the flux itself acts as a fluorescence enhancing reagent and buffer (maintaining the optimum pH of 7.1 ± 0.1). The fused melt of the flux mixture when dissolved in water, gives clear and stable solution. The accuracy and precision of the method was evaluated by analyzing Certified Reference Material, IGS-36 (Institute of Geological Sciences, UK) and monazite samples received from BSOI, Trivandrum. The accuracy of the data was further evaluated by comparing with conventional standard decomposition methods. The results are well within experimental error. RSD of the method is $\pm 2\%$ at 0.30% U_3O_8 in monazite minerals.

Keywords : Uranium, monazite, phosphate flux, LED fluorimeter.

Introduction

Monazite mineral is the main source of Rare Earth Elements (REE) and thorium. This refractory mineral is either of magmatic or pegmatitic origin and in India is found in the placer deposits of beach sands along with the heavy minerals like zircon, ilmenite, rutile, garnet, magnetite etc. During the crystallization of monazite mineral, some amounts of tetravalent thorium is replaced by tetravalent uranium due to their close ionic radii and same charge and the uranium content normally varies from 0.2 to 0.5% and in certain cases higher amounts are also common. In the industrial recovery process of REE and thorium¹ from monazite mineral, trace amounts of uranium accompany the REE and thorium fraction. Therefore evaluation of uranium content in these fractions is of significance at trace level.

The pellet fluorimetric determination of uranium after the ethyl acetate extraction is lengthy and cumbersome

hence results in low sample throughput. The various monazite mineral decomposition methods presently in vogue are (a) treatment with sulphuric acid¹, (b) fusion procedures involving sodium peroxide², mixture of potassium bi fluoride and sodium fluoride³ and potassium bi sulphate⁴. These fusion procedures introduce lot of unwanted salts apart from turning the solution acidic, hence the direct determination is not possible and require further processing before making measurements by laser/LED fluorimeter.

Radhamani *et al.*⁵ adopted a fusion method, using a mixture of tetra sodium pyro phosphate and mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate (1 : 1) and prepared the solution in 3% HCl to solubilise the insoluble Ce^{IV} polyphosphate. The presence of high amount of chloride quenches the fluorescence and uranium cannot be determined directly by using fluorimetric technique (Laser/LED). This method was modified by introducing addi-

tional reagent in the form of hydrogen peroxide to get clear solution and uranium was determined by using laser fluorimetric technique after adding sodium pyro phosphate solution (pH 7) as a fluorescence enhancing reagent⁶, thus involving use of additional reagent and additional steps. Hence the method became less rapid from sample high throughput point of view.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

All fluorescence measurements of uranium were made with a commercially available LED based fluorimeter, fabricated by M/s Quantalase Enterprises Pvt. Ltd., Indore, India. In this, a compact sealed-off light emitting diodes (LED) are used which emits very intense peak power of 1 watt UV pulses with a width of 20–30 micro seconds with repetition rate of 1000 Hz.

The pellet fluorimeter manufactured by ECIL, Hyderabad, India was also used for uranium measurements.

Reagents and standard solutions :

The standard stock solution of 1 mg/ml was prepared by fusing 0.1 g of U_3O_8 (prepared by igniting uranyl nitrate in a muffle furnace at 900 °C) with mixture of salts of sodium di hydrogen phosphate, di sodium hydrogen phosphate and tetra sodium pyro phosphate separately followed by dissolution in Milli-Q water. The working standards of 1, 2, 5 and 10 ng/ml were prepared by successive dilutions and matrix was matched by adding phosphate flux blank.

The salts of sodium di hydrogen phosphate and di sodium hydrogen phosphate, tetra sodium pyro phosphate used were of GR Merck make.

Milli-QTM water was used for all dilutions.

Procedure for monazite sample decomposition by three fusion methods :

(1) *Fusion method A :* Fusion with di sodium hydrogen phosphate and mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate.

Fifty milligram of sample was accurately weighed into a platinum crucible containing 2 g of mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate and 2 g of di sodium hydrogen phosphate (which was melted to remove moisture) and fused till the melt is red hot and clear. The cooled and solidi-

fied melt was transferred into a beaker containing distilled water and kept on water bath till the solution is clear and made up to 100 ml. As the fusion method and sample solution preparation takes about half an hour, it is recommended for monazite sample decomposition.

(2) *Fusion method B :* Fusion with mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate.

Fifty milligram of sample was accurately weighed into a platinum crucible containing 4 g of mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate (which was melted to remove moisture) and fused till the melt is red hot and clear. The cooled and solidified melt was transferred into a beaker containing distilled water and kept on water bath till the solution is clear and made up to 100 ml. The fusion method was also done using 2, 3 and 4 g of flux.

(3) *Fusion method C :* Fusion with tetra sodium pyro phosphate and mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate.

Fifty milligram of sample was accurately weighed into a platinum crucible containing 2 g of tetra sodium pyro phosphate and 2 g of sodium di hydrogen phosphate (which was melted to remove moisture) and fused till the melt is red hot and clear. The cooled and solidified melt was transferred into a beaker containing distilled water and kept on water bath till the solution is clear and made up to 100 ml. The fusion was also carried out using 3 and 4 g of flux (1 : 1).

The above three fusion methods were adopted for a standard reference material, IGS-36 and monazite samples received from BSOI, Trivandrum.

Determination of uranium by LED fluorimeter :

After suitable dilution of the sample solutions uranium was determined directly by LED based fluorimetric technique. Calibration standards were matrix matched. For standard addition, the respective phosphate blank (fusion methods A, B, C) solution was used for matrix matching.

Determination of uranium by pellet fluorimeter :

Three ml of the sample solution prepared as above was pipette out in an extraction vial and mixed with 15 ml of aluminum nitrate. Small quantity of fluoride is added to avoid extraction of thorium which is a quencher. The U was extracted by 10 ml ethyl acetate; suitable aliquot of extract was dried and fused with sodium fluoride and

sodium carbonate flux as per the standard procedure⁷. Fluorescence intensity was measured by conventional pellet fluorimeter.

Results and discussion

Monazite mineral is not completely decomposed by hydrofluoric and nitric acid digestion treatment hence fusion methods like sodium peroxide and potassium bi fluoride³ were adopted. In this method uranium cannot be determined directly by LED fluorimetric technique as the solution is acidic and contains high salt.

The fusion experiments were carried out using various combinations of phosphate fluxes in order to evaluate the suitable combinations of flux for effective and rapid fusion of monazite mineral, and the results are given in Table 1. The fusion with only sodium di hydrogen phosphate melts easily but pH has to be adjusted before measuring by LED fluorimetric technique. The mixture of tetra sodium pyro phosphate and sodium di hydrogen phosphate (1 : 1) takes about ten minutes time as against 5 min fusion time with sodium di hydrogen phosphate and di sodium hydrogen phosphate. More over the melt was not clear (not transparent), but the mixture of mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate and di sodium hydrogen phosphate (1 : 1) gave a very transparent melt resembling to honey colour.

Based on Table 1, the following observations are made :

In the fusion method A, fused melt obtained was clear and suitable for fluorescence measurement of uranium directly by LED fluorimetry without any pretreatment or adjustment of pH, as such pH of the solution is around 7.2. The solution is stable for measurements more than one month.

Table 1. Studies on various combinations of phosphate fluxes (Values in % U₃O₈)

Flux (g)	2 g	3 g	4 g	Reported value ^a
NaH ₂ PO ₄ +Na ₂ HPO ₄	Incomplete fusion	Incomplete fusion	0.296	0.290
NaH ₂ PO ₄	0.176	0.283	0.285	0.290
Na ₄ P ₂ O ₇ +NaH ₂ PO ₄	Incomplete fusion	0.270	0.282	0.290

^aDetermination by pellet fluorimetry after Na₂O₂ fusion.

In the fusion method B, where only mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate was used, 2 g flux was not sufficient for complete decomposition of the sample. Although 3 g of flux was sufficient, but fusion time was fifteen minutes as against ten minutes with the use of 4 g flux. The fused melt was not as clear as the melt obtained in fusion method A, and the pH was less than 7 after dissolution. So pH has to be adjusted before measurement by LED fluorimetry, hence decreasing sample throughput. Hence fusion method B is less preferred from high sample throughput point of view.

The fusion method C using 3 g flux, some turbidity was found after dissolution which resulted in low values of uranium. The decomposition with 4 g flux facilitated the complete decomposition of the monazite mineral and clear solution is prepared.

All the three fusion methods (A, B, C) were applied on monazite IGS-36 (supplied by Institute of Geological Sciences, UK) and monazite samples received from Beach Sand Offshore Investigations, Trivandrum and the results are given in Table 2. Based on above observations, optimal parameters have been fixed for complete decomposition and clear solution preparation for direct determination of uranium by LED based fluorimetric technique.

Table 2. Decomposition of monazite mineral by three fusion methods (% U₃O₈)

Sample No.	LED fluorimetry			Reported value ^a
	Fusion A	Fusion B	Fusion C	
IGS-36	0.294	0.258	0.270	0.288
Monazite-1	0.296	0.285	0.282	0.281
Monazite-2	0.362	0.342	0.357	0.340
Monazite-3	0.351	0.341	0.351	0.351
Monazite-4	0.344	0.335	0.343	0.350

^aBased on conventional pellet fluorimetry, Na₂O₂ fusion.

Fusion A : Mixture of di sodium hydrogen phosphate and mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate.

Fusion B : Mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate.

Fusion C : Mixture of tetra sodium pyro phosphate and mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate.

The mixture of sodium di hydrogen phosphate and di sodium hydrogen phosphate flux melts very easily and forms a clear melt when fused with sample. The solidified melt dissolved in hot water easily in about 30 min. The solution prepared is clear and highly stable. Because

of many characteristics of the flux like, ease of decomposition, dissolution and stability of the sample solution, authors have recommended the fusion of monazite sample with phosphate flux involving 2 g each of NaH_2PO_4 and Na_2HPO_4 for 50 mg sample. The method was applied on IGS-36 and some selected monazite samples of BSOI, Trivandrum. The results obtained are in close agreement with the values obtained by pellet fluorimetric method as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Evaluation of accuracy of proposed method by pellet fluorimetry

Sample	$\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 : \text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4$ 1 : 1 ratio of 2 g each	
	% $\text{U}_3\text{O}_8^{a(R)*}$	% $\text{U}_3\text{O}_8^{b*}$
IGS-36	0.294	0.291
Monazite-1	0.296	0.290
Monazite-2	0.362	0.346
Monazite-3	0.351	0.353
Monazite-4	0.344	0.345

^aLight Emitting Diode Fluorimetry, ^bPF - Pellet Fluorimetry, (R)Recommended method.
*Sample solution prepared by fusion with $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 : \text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4$ (1 : 1).

Effect of matrix elements :

Effect of major matrix elements on the concentration of uranium in the final measuring solution was studied. From the results, it was observed that the concentration of major matrix elements in the final measuring solution does not quench the fluorescence of uranium and the results are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Interference study of major matrix elements ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) on uranium fluorescence (5 ng/mL)

Sl. no.	Element	U_3O_8 (ng/mL)
1.	La (40 μg)	5
2.	Ce (80 μg)	5
3.	Pr (10 μg)	5
4.	Nd (30 μg)	5
5.	Sm (5 μg)	4.9
6.	Th (20 μg)	4.9
7.	All above (Mixed)	5

Total volume : 100 ml (contains 500 ng of U_3O_8).

Effect of phosphate on extraction of uranium :

Uranium was analysed in solutions prepared by fusion method A and by pellet fluorimetric technique after ethyl

acetate extraction. It was observed that uranium values are enhanced by 10 to 12%. But uranium values are agreeing well when compared with matrix match standards where the error is 1-2%.

High sample throughput :

Radhamani *et al.*⁸ used a fusion method, with a mixture of tetra sodium pyro phosphate and mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate (1 : 1) and prepared the solution in 3% HCl to solubilise the insoluble Ce(IV) polyphosphate. This method can't be applied directly for determination of uranium by LED fluorimetric techniques because chloride quenches uranyl fluorescence. The procedure further improved by Premadas *et al.*⁹ by addition of hydrogen peroxide to get a clear solution, which involve readjustment of pH to 7 for direct determination of uranium. Hence in both the methods direct determination of uranium by LED fluorimetry is not possible as it involves addition of reagents and readjustment to pH 7, hence less rapid which in turn results in low sample throughput.

The proposed method of fusing the monazite mineral with sodium di hydrogen phosphate and di sodium hydrogen phosphate is simple, rapid and direct for determination of U by LED fluorimetry as it does not involve skilled labour, addition of any other reagents to get a clear solution or pH adjustment to 7. Hence results in high sample throughput as about 24 monazite minerals could be determined for uranium in 8 working hours. The method is also ecofriendly as it does not require any acid for decomposition or dissolution; hence it does not evolve acidic fumes to the environment.

Accuracy and precision :

The accuracy of the proposed method was checked by analyzing uranium in certified reference material IGS-36 (Institute of Geological Sciences, UK) and the result is in good agreement with the certified value. The accuracy was further evaluated by analyzing uranium using pellet fluorimetry after the solutions prepared by proposed method and sodium peroxide fusion. The values obtained are in close agreement with the values obtained by proposed method and the results are given in Table 5. Relative standard deviation of the method is $\pm 2\%$ ($n=4$) at 0.30% U_3O_8 in monazite minerals.

Table 5. Evaluation of accuracy

Sample	Fusion A ^a	Fusion A ^a	Na ₂ O ₂ fusion
	LED F (% U ₃ O ₈)	P.F (% U ₃ O ₈)	P.F (% U ₃ O ₈)
IGS-36	0.294	0.291	0.288
Monazite-1	0.296	0.290	0.281
Monazite-2	0.362	0.346	0.340
Monazite-3	0.351	0.353	0.351
Monazite-4	0.344	0.345	0.350

LED F. – LED based fluorimetry, P.F – Pellet Fluorimetry.
^aProposed fusion method.

Conclusion

The proposed fusion method, with mono sodium di hydrogen phosphate and di sodium hydrogen phosphate (1 : 1) for the decomposition and dissolution of monazite mineral has many advantages over the existing fusion methods using Na₂O₂, KHF₂ and NaF, KHSO₄, etc. This method is very simple, decomposes and dissolves the monazite mineral completely in about ½ an hour. The clear solution obtained is stable. Uranium can be directly determined by LED based fluorimetric technique without adjusting pH or adding any fluorescence enhancing reagent. Hence large number of samples can be analysed in a short time which results in high sample throughput, when compared to reported fusion methods. The method is also ecofriendly as it does not evolve any acid fumes.

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